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Development of a 10-bit ultra-low power SAR ADC with programmable threshold in 130 nm CMOS technology

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ABSTRACT: The design and simulation results of an ultra-low power, fast 10-bit Successive Approximation Register (SAR) Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) in CMOS 130 nm technology are presented. This ADC is an extension of an experimentally verified 10-bit SAR ADC (INL, DNL < 0.5 LSB, ENOB > 9.5), working up to 50 MSps and consuming 680 μ W at 40 MSps. The goal of the present work was to add a programmable threshold for the processed input signal, to stop the conversion and thus greatly reduce power consumption in case the signal is below the threshold. The new ADC works up to around 40 MSps and consumes around 350 μ W at 40 MSps for low particle occupancy.

KEYWORDS: Analogue electronic circuits; Digital electronic circuits; Front-end electronics for detector readout

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1 Introduction

A fast, ultra-low power, area-efficient ADC is one of the essential components of a System on Chip (SoC) readout Application-Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) for particle physics detectors. In particular, an ultra-low power ADC with sampling rate reaching 40 MSps and medium to high resolution is required for multi-channel readout ASICs in modern and future Large Hadron Collider (LHC), or other, experiments. Such a 10-bit SAR ADC has already been developed in 130 nm CMOS technology [1] and has been successfully used in the readout ASICs [2–5] designed for various detectors in particle physics experiments.

The aim of this work was to improve the existing design [1] in such a way as to achieve significantly lower power consumption. The main idea was to add a programmable threshold for the processed input signal in order to stop the conversion in case the signal is below the threshold, and thus greatly reduce the power consumption. This extends the operating algorithm of the previous design, governed by asynchronous control logic, through an additional functionality implemented to compare the input signal to the ADC's threshold. This comparison adds an additional step to the conversion process; therefore, if the signal is above the threshold, the ADC conversion consists of 11 bit cycles, instead of 10. As a result, for signals above the threshold, the ADC is slightly slower and consumes a bit more power than the existing design. However, for signals below the threshold, the conversion is terminated immediately after the comparison, so the ADC is much faster and consumes significantly less power than the existing one.

In this work, the design and simulation results of the newly developed ultra-low power fast 10-bit SAR ADC with a programmable threshold in 130 nm CMOS technology are discussed.

2 Design of 10-bit SAR ADC

To achieve low power consumption, the SAR architecture was used in the design. A fully differential ADC architecture was chosen, comprising a pair of bootstrapped switches [6], a differential capacitive Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC) with the Merged Capacitor Switching (MCS) scheme [7], a dynamic comparator [8], and an asynchronous dynamic control logic. As a result of using components that operate only during conversion, static power was completely eliminated. To reduce total input capacitance, as well as power consumption, a split capacitor DAC scheme was applied, as seen in figure 1. A 6-1C-3 DAC segmentation was chosen with a 6-bit sub-DAC for the most significant bits,

Figure 1. Block diagram of 10-bit SAR ADC.

unit split capacitance, and a 3-bit sub-DAC for the least significant bits. That allowed achieving the lowest total capacitance within the constraints of the technology used. The difference from the previous ADC [1] is only in the SAR control logic, where a programmable threshold was added, as shown in figure 1. The ADC layout occupies an area of $560\ \mu\text{m} \times 80\ \mu\text{m}$, the same as the existing design.

2.1 Threshold implementation

After sampling the input signal, analogue-to-digital conversion begins. The sequence repeated for each bit begins with the activation of the comparator. Its response is stored as the value of the bit being processed, which then changes the configuration of the DAC switches and re-enables the comparator after a short delay needed for DAC output voltage settling. In the conventional design, this process is repeated ten times for a 10-bit resolution. In the proposed ADC design with a programmable threshold, the logic works in a different way.

The conversion process is illustrated in figure 2, where the differential signals at the comparator input and the ADC output are shown for a signal higher (left) and lower (right) than the threshold. An additional conversion cycle has been added to compare the input signal to a user-defined threshold, configurable with an 8-bit resolution. This comparison is only performed after the Most Significant Bit (MSB) has been determined, as a signal that exceeds the oxide breakdown voltage can potentially be applied to the comparator inputs otherwise. Switching of the DAC reference voltages, performed after the MSB conversion, reduces the sampled input voltage stored on the DAC top plates, ensuring that its sum with the threshold will never exceed the breakdown voltage limit. The threshold is then applied to the DAC by appropriately switching the reference voltages of the less significant bits. If the threshold voltage (V_{th}) is higher than the remaining signal and $MSB=0$, the conversion is ended, and all output bits are set to 0. However, if V_{th} is lower, the threshold is removed from the DAC, the conversion proceeds as normal, and the second most significant bit is determined. In the case of $MSB=1$, the condition of $V_{in} > V_{th}$ is always fulfilled by definition, so the conversion of the remaining bits ($D[8]-D[0]$) is always performed.

Comparison to the threshold can be disabled, allowing the ADC to operate as an existing ADC.

Figure 2. Example of ADC transient simulation for a signal higher (left) and lower (right) than the threshold. Signals $V_{cmp,p}$, $V_{cmp,n}$ are inputs to the comparator, while *Digital output* is the result of the ADC conversion. A grey background indicates the additional comparison cycle with the threshold.

3 Simulation results

The design was simulated at the schematic and post-layout level. In the beginning, simulations were performed at the schematic level to check the full ADC functionality. For quantitative understanding, both in terms of speed, power consumption, and resolution, post-layout simulations are relevant, and only the results of such simulations are presented in this work. The most important parameter is Effective Number of Bits (ENOB), which for this design is above 9.6 for any sampling rate within ADC operational range for the Nyquist input frequency, as shown in figure 3. Simulations of ENOB as a function of sampling frequency were performed with the threshold disabled (without threshold) and with the threshold set to 0 (with threshold $V_{in} > V_{th}$). The difference in maximum frequency is about 10 %, which is by the additional bit cycle in the threshold mode.

Figure 3. Effective number of bits versus sampling frequency.

The dependence of power consumption on sampling frequency is presented in figure 4, in two cases with the programmable threshold applied (for $V_{in} > V_{th}$ and $V_{in} < V_{th}$) and with the threshold functionality disabled. The fastest conversion (only 2 bit cycles) with the lowest possible power occurs in the mode with threshold in case of $V_{in} < V_{th}$. In contrast, the slowest conversion (11 bit cycles) with the highest power consumption takes place in the threshold mode, with the signal ($V_{in} > V_{th}$), which corresponds to the 100% hit occupancy.

Figure 4. Power consumption versus sampling frequency.

From the above results, it is clear that for low hit occupancy, it is possible to significantly reduce the power consumption using the threshold mode compared to the mode without threshold. The simulated power consumption as a function of the threshold, for several low hit occupancy values, is shown in figure 5. It can be noticed that for low occupancies, more than 50% of the power can be saved compared to operation without a threshold.

Figure 5. Power consumption versus threshold for different occupancies @40 MSps.

4 Summary

The design and simulations of a novel ultra-low power SAR ADC architecture with a programmable threshold have been presented. Post-layout simulations show that the designed SAR ADC works up to 40 MSps with ENOB above 9.6 and at low occupancy consumes about 350 μ W at 40 MSps. Since the existing ADC already had the lowest Figure of Merit (FOM) among state-of-the-art

designs with similar technology and specifications [1], using the presented ADC design with a programmable threshold, it is possible to reduce the FOM by more than 2 times, reaching a value close to 10 fJ/conv.-step previously unachievable in 130 nm CMOS technology. A prototype ASIC with several ADC channels implementing this novel architecture is in preparation and should be submitted to production in the near future.

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References

- [1] M. Firlej et al., *An ultra-low power 10-bit, 50 MSps SAR ADC for multi-channel readout ASICs*, 2023 *JINST* **18** P11013.
- [2] F. Bouyjou et al., *HGCROC3: the front-end readout ASIC for the CMS High Granularity Calorimeter*, 2022 *JINST* **17** C03015.
- [3] T. Niknejad et al., *Results with the TOFHIR2X Revision of the Front-end ASIC of the CMS MTD Barrel Timing Layer*, in the proceedings of the 2021 IEEE Nuclear Science Symposium (NSS) and Medical Imaging Conference (MIC) and 28th International Symposium on Room-Temperature Semiconductor Detectors, Piscataway, NJ, U.S.A. (2021), p. 1–5 [DOI:10.1109/NSS/MIC44867.2021.9875751].
- [4] J. Moroń, *FLAME SoC readout ASIC for electromagnetic calorimeter*, in the proceedings of the Topical Workshop on Electronics for Particle Physics (TWEPP2022), Bergen, Norway, 19–23 September 2022 [https://indico.cern.ch/event/1127562/contributions/4904506/].
- [5] S. Conforti Di Lorenzo et al., *HKROC: an integrated front-end ASIC to readout photomultiplier tubes for the Hyper-Kamiokande experiment*, 2023 *JINST* **18** C01035.
- [6] M. Dessouky and A. Kaiser, *Input switch configuration suitable for rail-to-rail operation of switched opamp circuits*, *Electron. Lett.* **35** (1999) 8.
- [7] V. Hariprasath, J. Guerber, S.-H. Lee and U.-K. Moon, *Merged capacitor switching based SAR ADC with highest switching energy-efficiency*, *Electron. Lett.* **46** (2010) 620.
- [8] H.J. Jeon, Y.-B. Kim and M. Choi, *Offset voltage analysis of dynamic latched comparator*, in the proceedings of the 2011 IEEE 54th International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS), Seoul, Korea (2011), p. 1–4 [DOI:10.1109/mwscas.2011.6026358].